

EXPLORING THE BENEFITS OF USING AUTHENTIC MATERIALS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE INSTRUCTION

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Abstract: This article provides information about authentic materials. It also explains the types of authentic materials and how to use them in teaching. In addition, the importance of authentic materials in teaching and how to adapt them to lessons will be discussed. This article gives several resources and guidelines for the use of these materials, taking into account the research of scientists. Based on these sources, authentic materials are detailed.

Key words: authentic materials, real, teaching, teacher, education, written, spoken, visual, learners

Аннотация: В этой статье представлена информация об аутентичных материалах. В нем также объясняются типы аутентичных материалов и способы их использования в обучении. Кроме того, будет обсуждаться важность аутентичных материалов в обучении и способы их адаптации к урокам. В этой статье приведены несколько ресурсов и рекомендации по использованию этих материалов с учетом исследований ученых. На основе этих источников подробно изложены аутентичные материалы.

Ключевые слова: аутентичные материалы, реальное, преподавание, учитель, образование, пишт, разговорный, визуальный, учащихся

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada haqiqiy materiallar haqida ma'lumot berilgan. Shuningdek, u haqiqiy materiallarning turlarini va ulardan o'qitishda qanday foydalanishni tushuntiradi. Bundan tashqari, o'qitishda autentik materiallarning ahamiyati va ularni darsga moslashtirish masalalari muhokama qilinadi. Ushbu maqolada olimlarning tadqiqotlarini hisobga olgan holda ushbu materiallardan foydalanish bo'yicha bir nechta manbalar va ko'rsatmalar berilgan. Ushbu manbalarga asoslanib, haqiqiy materiallar batafsil bayon etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: haqiqiy materiallar, asl, o'qitish, o'qituvchi, ta'lim, yozma, og'zaki, ko'rib o'rgansa bo'ladigan, o'rganuvchilar

In today's modern world, the demand for learning English is increasing. Therefore, during language teaching, the teacher tries to use many useful materials for his students. These materials should serve not only to increase students' knowledge and interest them in English language. Authentic materials, unlike teaching materials, have their place in education. But they were not created primarily for education.

"Authentic Materials: An Overview (2002)" by Alejandro G. Martinez deals with the term authentic materials itself and with advantages and disadvantages of their use as well as possible sources of them. Authentic materials- Sometimes called authentic or contextualized, real-life materials are those that a student encounters in everyday life but that weren't created for educational purposes. They include newspapers, magazines, and Web sites, as well as drivers manuals, utility bills, pill bottles, and clothing labels. Martinez listed following benefits:

Students are exposed to real language

There is factual acquisition from most of them

Textbooks do not include inaccurate language

Authentic materials may be inspirational for some students

One piece of text may be used for various activities and tasks

There is a wide choice of styles, genres and formality in authentic texts

They can motivate students to read for pleasure¹

Taking into account the advantages of the above-mentioned authentic materials, it is possible to make sure that these materials can be used effectively in the classroom. Because although these materials are not adapted for education, there is a possibility of integration into any field, including teaching. Authentic materials can be written, spoken, or visual, and they can cover a wide range of topics and genres, such as news, entertainment, education, business, travel, or sports.

The use of real materials in the lesson is definitely beneficial for both the teacher and the student. Authentic materials also offer authentic and understandable ways for current users of the language. In addition, it teaches students ways to learn the language through their areas of interest. Authentic materials also help bridge cross-cultural diversity. If students use authentic materials during language learning, they will also learn about the culture of the language they are learning.

¹Authentic Materials: An Overview by Alejandro G. Martinez. 2002. 34 p

We have to be very careful when using authentic materials. Because not every real material may be suitable for teaching. Also, the level of the actual materials should match the level of the students. English as a second language learners should make sure that authentic materials are reliable when using them. Because it is very important that the real materials are reliable.

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